

HORSE-RELATED TRADITIONS IN THE MIRZACHUL OASIS IN THE XX-EARLY XXI CENTURIES

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Abstract. *This article provides some information about the traditions of the people of Mirzachul oasis, which are associated with horses, and their significance is different. In the study of the historical landscape of the Mirzachul oasis in the XX - early XXI centuries, this article provides a lot of material.*

Keywords: *Mirzachul, old saddle, "tebingi", "ayil", "kuyushkon", "omildirik", "kanjiga", "uzangi", "taralgi".*

ТРАДИЦИИ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ЛОШАДЯМИ, В МИРЗАЧУЛЬСКОМ ОАЗИСЕ В XX - НАЧАЛЕ XXI ВВ.

Аннотация. *В данной статье приведены некоторые сведения о традициях жителей Мирзачульского оазиса, которые связаны с лошадьми, и их значение различно. В изучении исторического ландшафта Мирзачульского оазиса в XX - начале XXI веков данная статья дает большой материал.*

Ключевые слова: *Мирзачул, старое седло, «тебинги», «айыл», «куюшкон», «омилдирик», «канджига», «узанги», «таралги».*

INTRODUCTION

The economic and cultural life of the rural population in almost all countries of Central Asia, including various regions and districts of Uzbekistan the special place of cattle and horses in their lives is striking. In particular, the fact that various ceremonies and traditions associated with horse breeding have retained their significance to this day, indicates that the ancient traditions in the economic life of the peoples of the region still continue. It is noteworthy that many traditions of the Mirzachul oasis villagers, such as the efficient use of horses, breeding horses, training horses for goats, feeding horses and making equipment for horseback riding, have been preserved to some extent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As in all historical and cultural regions of Central Asia, the Mirzachul oasis is popular among the population, especially among the population of the oasis, which in the past was dominated by nomadic cattle breeding, such as Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz. it should be noted that it is somewhat well preserved. It is known that in the Turkic peoples there are many types of saddles, ie equipment used for horseback riding, which are divided into such types as "old saddle", "men's saddle", "women's saddle", "children's saddle", depending on their use in everyday life.

Also, saddles are called "birch saddle", "pine saddle", "iron saddle", etc. in connection with the material from which they are made, "golden saddle", "silver saddle", "silver saddle", iron saddle "and" patterned saddle ". In addition, depending on the shape of the saddles in the Turkic peoples can be divided into "saddle saddle", "spread saddle", "large saddle", "small saddle", "saddle / saddle saddle", "remaining saddle", "unopened saddle" and so on. available.

The study examines the historiography of the study of a number of traditions and terms associated with the horse in the Mirzachul oasis on the basis of methods of comparative, historical and hermeneutic analysis.

RESULTS

Mirzachul oasis is mainly used by Uzbeks, Kazakhs and Kyrgyz, and partly by Tajiks for saddles and other horse harnesses. ”;“ Uzangi ”;“ tarolgi ”or“ uzangi bag ”;“ yugan / jugan ”;“ chilvir ”;“ tizgin ”;“ nokhta ”;“ suvlik ”;“ oguzlik ”and a number of other subject names. As will be discussed in more detail below, in almost all Turkic peoples the words related to saddles and other horse equipment are used in the same form, but their function and form of construction are quite common.

1. Ail is a braided strap that is tied around the top of the saddle around the horse's belly¹.
2. A sign is a horse that is placed under a jazz².
3. Dikkak - dikdikka, dig-diga. Decorative, pop-covered, tossed on horseback; jul³.
4. Jazlik - A pair of soft horse harnesses that can be placed under a saddlebag⁴.
5. Jahaldirik is a type of jazz⁵.
6. The bridle is the leather handle of the yugan⁶
7. Bubble - A pillow to put under the saddle⁷.
8. Point - A horse harness worn on the head to tie, lead, and drive a horse⁸
9. Mouth – watery⁹.
10. Pushtan - a belt that is tied around the saddle of a horse¹⁰.
10. Water is a piece of metal that is put in a horse's mouth¹⁰.
11. Knitting - a leather thread from the saddle to the stirrup, garden¹¹.
12. Tarolgi¹².
13. Slippers - a thick piece of felt that is placed under the saddle to prevent the skin of the horse from getting into the tissue¹³.
14. Tizgin - reins. Horse, donkey, etc. b. a ribbon or rug that serves to tie or untie animals, the end of which is attached to a watercolor or headband¹⁴.
15. Woven - A harness made of felt, usually placed under a saddle or saddle¹⁵.
16. Buckle - a part of the belt, belt, etc., which passes through the end¹⁶.
17. Omildirik - a metal ornament worn on the chest of a horse. Burial -. Two in Devonu lug'ati-t-turk¹⁷1) "ornaments on the horse's chest", 2) "something tied to the saddle by the horse's shoulders so that the load does not go back".
18. Stirrup - A metal horse harness that is fastened to both sides of the saddle with a strap and used to ride a horse and keep the legs on the saddle¹⁸.
19. Uzma - a metal ornament worn on the neck¹⁹.
20. Hook, hook - a strap, tie or hook attached to the back of a saddle to tie a load and other things²⁰.
21. Qoptol - side. To approach from the side, to approach, to be at a very close distance from the side²¹.
22. The eyebrow is the place where something is pushed, the eyebrow of the horse's saddle²².
23. A strap is a strap that is attached to a saddle by twisting it under the tail of a horse or donkey to prevent the saddle from moving forward, often with various ornaments²³.
24. Chilvir - a thin twisted rope, rope; drawing²⁴

25. Chirgi - slippers, closed²⁵.

Yugan is a device made of water, reins and belts that are put on the heads of horses, donkeys and other animals to control them.

27. While a significant portion of these terms are understandable to a large portion of the population, to date some segments of the population, particularly those living in urban and district centers, have become young who do not understand the literal meaning of these words.

28. It is known that the front and back eyebrows of the saddle, that is, the place where the upper edges of the saddle are pushed. The cushion under the saddle is called a "bubble" and the thick "belt" that is pulled along the horse's thick belly is called a "pushton". Bedding under the saddle – double.

DISCUSSION

(flat) A flat felt object under the "bag" (on both sides) is called a "tissue". The fabric is 120-130 cm long and 60 cm wide and is made of cooked "living wool". "Live wool" refers to the wool obtained from the autumn shearing of a lamb born in the spring. The felt fabric is often covered with leather, and the edges are sewn tightly with a woven fabric.

CONCLUSION

The ayil is a wide-joint harness that holds the saddle on the horse and is pulled along the horse's belly. It is also called "tosh-ayil" or "chap-ayil" (back ayil) depending on the position it performs. The pelvis is pulled close to the front legs of the horse's abdomen. The left hemisphere is longer than the right hemisphere. Usually when the chest is tightly tied, the left-handed is pulled loosely so as not to cut the horse's saddle. The Kazakh people say, "He does not know the value of his brother." "He does not know the value of his brother, he knows it."

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